

Democratic Backsliding in Tunisia

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Using the case of Tunisia, I look at a single aspect of democratic backsliding: its relationship with women's political representation. At the level of political leadership, the Tunisia case highlights that women can play prominent and symbolically important roles in anti-democratic movements and in episodes of democratic backsliding. But when we turn to female representation more broadly, the Tunisia case shows how declines in female representation can presage democratic backsliding and how democratic backsliding can further undermine women's political representation.

On July 25, 2021, Tunisia's president, Kais Saied, invoked the emergency clause of the constitution, suspending the parliament and dismissing the country's prime minister, Hichem Mechichi. In late September 2021, two months after his power grab, Saied appointed Najla Bouden as the prime minister, Tunisia's first female prime minister (AlJazeera 2021). Some viewed this as an attempt to "pinkwash" Saied's power grab, using a female leader to counter the perceptions of the move as authoritarian (Ben-Shitrit et al. 2021a, Ben-Shitrit et al. 2021b). This aligns with existing research demonstrating that autocracies adopt pro-women policies or increase women's political representation in order to increase international and domestic legitimacy (Tripp 2019, Bjarnegård and

Zetterberg 2022).

Despite female representation at one of the highest levels of Tunisian politics following Saied's power grab, there is evidence from the country of a negative association between democratic backsliding and women's representation. Figure 1 shows Tunisia's V-Dem score and female representation from 2000 until 2023. Focusing on the period from 2019 to 2023, two patterns warrant further exploration: (1) a decline in women's political representation foreshadowed Saied's *autogolpe* and (2) women's political representation continued to decline after the autocratic power grab. These patterns suggest a relationship between democratic backsliding and reduced opportunities for women's political participation that merits further investigation.

During the 2011 elections for the National Constituent Assembly held in the aftermath of the popular revolution that brought down Tunisia's Ben Ali regime, women won 59 seats out of 217, thanks to a vertical parity requirement stipulated in the country's new electoral law (The Carter Center 2011, Cherif 2014). The number of female deputies elected increased during the 2014 parliamentary elections when women won 68 out of 217 seats (The Carter Center 2014, Clark et al. 2024).

Figure 1: Democratic Backsliding and women's representation in Tunisia, 2000-2023

During the 2019 elections, however, women's political representation decreased significantly, with women winning only 49 of the 217 seats (The Carter Center 2019). This decline in women's political representation was in part the result of growing alienation from the country's main political parties, a trend that contributed to Saied's power grab in 2021. In 2014, only four parties had more than 10 representatives in parliament, while in 2019, seven parties had more than 10 representatives and the major parties were in decline (IPU 2024). This alienation from the main political parties meant that fewer candidates from any one electoral list in a particular constituency won a seat, and, since women were rarely the heads of the electoral list, this fractionalization had a particularly adverse effect on women's representation.¹

1 If we calculate political representation fractionalization (the probability that two randomly drawn MPs from the elected parliament belong to two different parties), it is roughly .73 in 2014 and .87 in 2019. This reinforces the idea that the parliament is more fractionalized in 2019. The relationship between weak party institutionalization and low female representation is discussed in Wylie (2018) and Belschner (2022).

Following the 2021 autogolpe, President Saied pushed through a new constitution and new electoral laws, stipulating a majoritarian electoral system rather than proportional representation. The first elections held under this new system in December 2022 and January 2023 witnessed a further decline in female political representation. The percentage of female MPs dropped from 22.6 percent in 2019 to 16.2 percent in 2023 (IPU 2024). This underlines how strategies aimed at executive aggrandizement – common in cases of democratic backsliding – can contribute to a decline in women's political representation. Moreover, cases of democratic backsliding like Tunisia also include a substantial crackdown on civil society, including women's organizations, which often mobilize for female

political candidates during elections.

The Tunisian case highlights the complex relationship between democratic backsliding and female representation. While women may attain prominent roles in anti-democratic movements and episodes of democratic backsliding, broader female representation often suffers. The case of women's representation and democratic backsliding in Tunisia demonstrates that the erosion of one often leads to the decline of the other. ♦

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